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No Fringe Benefit Tax Payable on Medical Reimbursement

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Abstract

“Medical reimbursement up to Rs.15000 is chargeable to tax as fringe benefit in the hands of employer” has mentioned which answering question 69 in CBDT circular 8/2005 dated 29th August 2005. This was analysed by article and related CBDT circulars and other similar issues and puts forward the viewpoint that no fringe benefit tax is payable by the employer on medical reimbursement facility provided to employees

Keywords Medical Reimbursement, Perquisite, Fringe Benefit.

Introduction

The Finance Bill 2005 introduces the fringe benefit tax , the employer is now liable to pay the tax in respect of certain fringe benefits. These fringe benefits were taxable as perquisites are no longer taxable in the hands of employees. For this, the rules for valuation of perquisite have been amended vide notification no. 68/2005, whereby following rules of valuation of perquisite have been withdrawn.

1. Rule 2 for valuation of moter car.
2. Rule 3 relating to valuation of travelling, free meal, credit card, club facility, etc.

Objective of study

1. To determine the financial impact of providing medical reimbursement without incurring fringe benefit tax.
2. To understand how the non-taxable nature of medical reimbursement affects the attractiveness of the company as an employer.

Review of Literature

Fringe benefit tax levied on employers for certain non-cash benefits provided to employees. As per the general understanding of tax laws in many countries, the concept of FBT (Fringe Benefit Tax) aims to bring non-cash perks into the tax net. Medical reimbursement is a common employee benefit where employees reimburse employers for medical expenses incurred. It is considered an important part of the employer's welfare package and helps in reducing the financial burden of medical costs.

Main Text

Mutual Exclusion Between Perquisite and Fringe Benefit Tax

Finance Act, 2005 has amended clause (VI) of section 17(2) ,which is read as “the value of any other fringe benefit and amenity (excluding the fringe benefit chargeable to tax

under chapter XII-H) as may be prescribed. 'Prior to this amendment Clause VI was read as the 'value of any other fringe benefit or amenity as may be prescribed'.

Thus this clause has been amended to provide that only those fringe benefits and amenities shall be included in the perquisite chargeable to tax in the hands of employee which are not chargeable to tax as fringe benefit tax in the hands of employer. It means that those fringe benefits and amenities on which tax is payable by the employer as fringe benefit tax shall not be included as perquisite in the hands of employee.

Sub-section (3) of section 115WB is read as for the purpose of sub section (1) the privilege, service, facility or amenity does not include perquisite in respect of which tax is paid or payable by employee Thus, any facility or amenity chargeable to tax as perquisite in the hands of employee cannot be taxed as fringe benefit tax in the hands of employer.

In this way there is mutual exclusion between the two. If the facility or amenity is chargeable to tax as perquisite in the hands of employee, the same cannot be taxed as fringe benefit in the hands of employer in view of sub section (3) of section 115WB. Similarly, if the facility or amenity is chargeable to tax as fringe benefit in the hands of employer, the same cannot be taxed as perquisite in the hands of employees in view of amended clause (VI) of sub section (2) of section 17.

In view of sub section (3) of section 115WB, facility or amenity which is chargeable as perquisite in the hands of employees, cannot be taxed as fringe benefit in the hands of employer. Similarly, facility or amenity chargeable as fringe benefit in the hands of employer can not be taxed as perquisite in the hands of employees in view of amended clause (VI) of sub section(2) of section 17 of the Act.

Taxation of Medical Facility Provided by Employer to Employee

As per provision clause (VI) of sub section 2 of section 17 of Act, Medical facility is chargeable to tax as perquisite in the hands of employee. Clause(V) of the above proviso has provided that the medical reimbursement in excess of Rs.15000 is chargeable to tax in the hands of employee as perquisite. [1] However, CBDT circular 8/2005 dated 29th August, 2005, while answering Question 69, has mentioned that medical reimbursement up to Rs. 15000 is chargeable to tax as fringe benefit in the hands of employer. The text of Question 69 of the above circular is as follows:

'Whether medical reimbursement up to Rs. 15000(exempt in the hands of the employees) and medical reimbursement over Rs. 15000 (taxed as perquisite in the hands of the employee) is liable to FBT ?

69, At present ,if any sum is paid by the employer for expenditure actually incurred by the employee for medical treatment in an unapproved hospital and it exceeds Rs. 15000 during the year , such sum is salary as defined in clause (1) of section 17 of income tax Act and liable to income tax in the hands of the employee. There is no change in this position. Since such sum is taxable in the hands of the employee, the same is not liable to FBT.

However, if any sum is paid by the employer for expenditure actually incurred by the employee for medical treatment in an unapproved hospital and it does not exceed Rs. 15000 during the year, such sum does not fall within the meaning of salary as defined in clause (1) of section 17 of the Income tax Act and not liable to income tax in the hands of the employee. There is no change in this position. Since such sum is not taxable in the hands of the employee, the same is liable to FBT.'

Thus, the above circular provides that medical reimbursement up to Rs. 15000 is chargeable to tax as fringe benefit tax in the hands of employer and as per proviso to clause (VI) of sub section 2 section 17 the medical reimbursement above Rs.15000 is chargeable as perquisite in the hands of employee. Is this right that some part of the same facility is chargeable to tax as fringe benefit tax in the hands of employer and remaining part is chargeable to tax as perquisite in the hands of employee ?

Employees has to pay tax on the facility or amenity received by the employees from employer. Fringe benefit tax is on obligation of employees borne by employer. If there would not be fringe benefit tax, employees would not required to pay tax on medical reimbursement up to Rs. 15000.

Contradictory CBDT Circular

CBDT circular 8/2008 is contradictory to the provision of sub section(3) of section 115WB because as per proviso to the clause(VI) of sub section 2 of section 17 of the Act, medical facility is chargeable to tax as perquisite in the hands of employee. Therefore, the same cannot be taxed as fringe benefit in the hands of employer [section115(3)].

Applicability of CBDT Circular

The circular cannot override provisions of the Act. Section 119 has empowered CBDT to issue orders, instructions or directions for the 'proper administration' of the Act. Such an order, instruction or direction cannot override the provisions of the Act. [2]

Medical reimbursement is chargeable as perquisite in the hands of employee as per clause (v) of the proviso to the clause (VI) of sub section(2) of section 17 of the Act. While including the same in the taxable income of employee , exemption of Rs. 15000 is given .Thus ,an exemption of Rs. 15000 is given in the Act. The CBDT circular (No 8/2005) has mentioned that payment of fringe benefit tax on medical reimbursement of Rs. 15000 is amounting to amending the provision of the Act , which is passed in Parliament. Thus, this CBDT circular directing authority to charge medical reimbursement up to Rs. 15000 as fringe benefit in the hands of employer is ultra virus.

Binding nature of circulars- CBDT circular is binding on revenue even though the circular is deviation from the provision of the Act.[3] However CBDT circular is not binding on Appellate Authority or Tribunal or Court or Assessee.[4]

Fringe Benefit Tax an Obligation of Employee

Employee receives privileges, service, benefit or amenity by the employer. Therefore, employee pays tax on these facilities or amenities. Fringe benefit tax is an obligation of the employee borne by employer. So, if there would not be fringe benefit tax, employees would not be required to pay tax on medical reimbursement up to Rs. 15000.[5] Thus, payment of fringe benefit tax by the employer medical reimbursement is amounting to double taxation.

Conclusion

If CBDT issues another circular by amending the above circular to provided that employer will not pay fringe benefit tax on medical reimbursement of Rs.15000. To sum up, no fringe benefit tax is payable by the employer on medical reimbursement facility provided to employees.

References

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4. *CIT vs. Hero Cycles (P.) Ltd. [1997] 94 Taxman 271/228 ITR463 (SC)*
5. *R. K. Jain and CA. Nikhil Gupta, Income Tax: Law & Accounts*